

1 pedro-open-dataset: a combination of code datasets

The pedro-open-dataset is a code dataset with 22,000 lines. It mainly contains Python code (but also code in other programming languages) and uses an instruction-response format, meaning it only contains instructions and responses. It is licensed under a permissive license called BSD 3-Clause, but it is a combination of datasets licensed under Apache 2.0 and CC-BY 4.0.

1.1 Why does it exist?

The pedro-open-dataset exists to provide a simple and clear code dataset.

1.2 How was it built?

The Pedro Open Dataset was built using three datasets:

- Vezora/Tested-22k-Python-Alpaca
- CyberNative/Code_Vulnerability_Security_DPO
- MCES10-Software/Python-Code-Solutions

1.3 What are the applications of this dataset?

The pedro-open-dataset was created for fine-tuning and training AI models, although it can also be used for research.

1.4 Additional Information

- **Dataset link:** <https://huggingface.co/datasets/pedrodev2026/pedro-open-dataset>
- **Dataset license:** BSD 3-Clause
- **Dataset licenses used:** Apache 2.0, CC-BY 4.0
- **Author:** Pedro Lucas
- **Paper license:** CC-BY 4.0
- **Paper license link:** <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>